

Optical Communications Through Low Orbit Satellites

Joan Carles Montero

Maths Student

Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

Mataró, Spain

joancarles.monteroj@autonoma.cat

Mercè Feliu

Science Department

Laia Arquera High School

Mataró

mfeliu25@xtec.cat

Joan Bas

Array & Multi-Sensor Processing Department

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions (CTTC)

Castelldefels, Spain

joan.bas@cttc.es

Abstract—Current societal needs demand for global high-speed networks. Toward this regard, 3GPP has included in its release 17 Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN). In order to meet the strict requirements of 6G networks, Very Low Earth Orbit (VLEO) and Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites will play a key role. Optical fibers can also be used for transmitting data at high speeds. Unfortunately, the refraction index of the optical fibers and the satellite altitude penalize them. So, this paper determines the transmission distance for which it is better to use optical fiber or satellite links. For a fair comparison in terms of bandwidth, it has been assumed that the LEO/VLEO satellites should be optical too. After that an algorithm has been developed to determine the best suitable regions for locating the ground station of an optical satellite. Specifically, it computes the degree of cloudiness of a certain geographic region. Given that the determination of such regions demands a large computational burden, it has been parallelized using OpenMP libraries for Python. The Iberian Peninsula, which images were taken by the METEOSAT satellite from EUMETSAT, has been considered as a paradigmatic case of study.

Index Terms—New communication technologies; Optical LEO Satellites; Optical fiber; 5G; 6G; Propagation time reduction; Parallel algorithms; Science education; STEM.

I. INTRODUCTION.

This paper results from the collaboration between a research center¹ and a high school². Therefore, the introduction will be divided in two parts: i) introduction to the educational framework that has motivated this collaboration, and ii) the technical introduction to the paper. The next sub-sections detail them.

A. Educational Framework of This Research Project.

The baccalaureate, awarded at the high schools, is part of the post-compulsory secondary education, and it is distributed over two academic years. It has the following three modalities: i) *the scientific-technological one*, ii) *the humanistic-social one*, and iii) *the artistic one*. Usually, it addresses students from ages 16 to 18 years. Since 2008, it is mandatory that high school students from Catalonia conduct a research work. It is regulated by the educational decree 142/2008 at the DOGC

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²Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya, CTTC

³Institut Laia Arquera, Mataró, Spain

(Official Gazette of the Generalitat de Catalunya) [1] and the educational order EDU/554/2008 [2]. This research work is a set of structured and research-oriented activities carried out by all high school students with the guidance and monitoring of teachers to consolidate their competences in the area of research. It can either be framed in a single discipline or in multiple ones (*i.e.* cross-sectorial). According to [1] the dedication in hours of baccalaureate students to their research work is of 70 hours, which will be carried out between the end of their first course and the beginnings of their second one. The topic of the research work is chosen by the students in conjunction with the teachers of their institutes. Regarding the work presented in this conference, Laia Arquera school contacted with CTTC to establish a solid bridge between a cutting edge research center and an outstanding pedagogical institution. This type of relationship is aligned with the actions that European Union (EU) conducts to promote top-down dissemination activities of its research programs. Examples of those are the Mary Curie actions (*e.g.* European Researchers' Night) [3], Tecniospring research programs from Generalitat de Catalunya [4], to name a few of them which foment research habits to young students.

B. Technical Introduction.

According to the Ericsson Mobility Report [5], Massive IoT technologies based on NB-IoT and Cat-M are increasing and during 2021, they will reach close to 330 million of connections. Furthermore, it is forecast that in 2026 these technologies will make up to 46% of all cellular IoT connections, having a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of around 23%. Towards this regard, 3GPP has planned in its Rel. 17 to integrate Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) to increase the capacity, wide-area coverage, scalability, service continuity, and availability of current 5G terrestrial networks [6].

Given the necessity for providing lower service times in 5G & beyond/6G networks, the data plane has moved from the traditional GEO satellites to the LEO/VLEO ones. Nevertheless, optical fiber networks are also able to transport data at high speeds. Unfortunately, their refraction index is much larger than the free space one ($n_{\text{space}} \approx 1$) [7]. Typical refraction indexes of the core and cladding in a single mode fiber (SMF)

are $n_{\text{core}}=1.48$ and $n_{\text{cladding}}=1.46$ respectively [7]. So, there is a limit distance in which it is preferable to use optical fiber (satellite) rather than satellite (optical fiber) links. This paper determines this distance. Toward this regard, [8]–[10] have compared the latency of multiple satellite links regarding optical fiber when it is desired to connect several cities. The results show that it is possible to obtain a routing algorithm that minimizes the latency compared to a direct connection using optical fiber. Nonetheless, they do not provide any closed-formula of the latency nor mathematical analysis to determine it. For that reason, the present work tries to shed light on this issue. Furthermore, it has been developed an algorithm to locate the optimal geographical areas for placing an optical ground station. As a paradigmatic case, it has been considered the Iberian Peninsula as the region where to collocate such optical ground station. EUMETSAT's³ weather and climate monitoring system from space has provided the images of the Iberian Peninsula [11]. Images from the years 2011 to 2019 have been analyzed. Given that it represents a huge amount of data, the developed program has been parallelized using OpenMP libraries for Python [12].

Finally, this paper has the following sections. Section II provides the scenario and propagation time signal models for transmissions through LEO/VLEO and optical fiber networks. Section III explains the algorithm for determining the regions with the lowest cloud probability and its efficient parallel architecture for speeding the location algorithm up. Finally, sections IV and V provide the main outcomes and conclusions of this paper respectively.

II. SCENARIO AND PROPAGATION TIME SIGNAL MODELS.

The goal of this section is threefold: i) to explain the scenario for transmitting data over satellite and optical fiber networks, ii) to present their propagation time models, and iii) to compute the minimum distance for which it is better to use optical/satellite links for having minimum propagation time. The next sections detail these.

A. Scenario Definition.

There are two locations, A and B that have to be connected using a high-speed network, two ways of connecting them: i) via optical fiber, or ii) via a satellite link (See Fig. 1) and we can only use one of them. *What criteria do we have to follow to use one or other high-speed network?* To answer this question it is assumed that the curvature of Earth is spherical. For the sake of simplicity, it has been considered that the satellite is in the middle of the arc that define the locations A and B . So, if the distance from location (point) A to the satellite, S , is denoted as $l_{A,S}$, by symmetry the distance from the satellite to location (point) B will be the same, $l_{B,S} = l_{A,S} = l$. Then, the total distance that the waves travel using the satellite link is, $d_{A,S,B}=2l$. On the contrary, if we connect the locations (points) A and B by means of optical fiber their separation is: $d_{A,B}=2R_E\beta$, where R_E is the average radius of Earth (*i.e.* $R_E=6.371$ Km) and β , the so-called *interior angle*.

Figure 1. Representation of the data transmission flow considering curvature of Earth.

This angle can be determined by applying the cosine theorem to the triangle defined by the center of Earth, O , the satellite, S , and point B , \overline{OSB} as:

$$\beta = \cos^{-1} \left[\frac{R_E^2 + (R_E + h)^2 - l^2}{2R_E(R_E + h)} \right]. \quad (1)$$

being h and α the altitude and elevation angle of the satellite respectively (See Fig.1). This elevation angle is related to the *interior angle* β as:

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2} - \beta - \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{R_E \sin(\beta)}{R_E + h - R_E \cos(\beta)} \right). \quad (2)$$

After having defined the proposed scenario, the next section details the propagation time models.

B. Propagation Time Signal Model.

In order to determine the propagation time signal models it is necessary to remark that the optical and satellite links have different refraction indexes. The refraction indexes of the core and cladding for a single modal fiber (SMF) are $n_{\text{core}}=1.48$ and $n_{\text{cladding}}=1.46$ respectively [7] whereas in the free-space case (*i.e.* vacuum) it is the unity, $n_{\text{fs}}=1$. From these values, it is obtained that then the velocity of the waves over optical fiber is around 30% lower than over free space links (*i.e.* $(n_{\text{of}} - n_{\text{fs}})/n_{\text{fs}} \times 100$). Thereby, the waves through satellite links travel larger distances than through optical fiber and may arrive earlier to their final destination. On the contrary, if the distance $d_{A,B}$ is short, the large altitudes of the satellite orbits penalizes them over the optical fibers. Consequently, both technologies will be complementary for transmitting data at high speeds. Then, their propagation time for transmitting data from point A to point B will be:

$$T_{\text{of}} = \frac{d_{A,B}}{\left(\frac{c}{n_{\text{of}}}\right)} ; \quad T_{\text{fs}} = \frac{d_{A,S,B}}{c}, \quad (3)$$

being c , T_{of} , and T_{fs} the light-speed, propagation time of the optical fiber and satellite respectively. Finally, after having

³European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites

Figure 2. Propagation time of satellite and the optical fiber when the altitude of satellite, h , is 600Km and 1200Km in terms of the distance A-B, $d_{A,B}$.

determined the propagation time of the optical and satellite links we proceed to compute the minimum one among them.

C. Minimum Propagation Time Selection.

As we have shown, the values taken for the distance between points A and B , $d_{A,B}$, the altitude of the satellite, h , and the refraction index of the optical fiber, n_{of} , calculate which transmission media to select. If points A and B were connected using the optical network, then its propagation time, T_{of} , should obey:

$$T_{of}(d_{A,B}) < T_{fs}(d_{A,S,B}). \quad (4)$$

Otherwise, it would be better to use the satellite network. However, the distance that the waves travel using the satellite link, $d_{A,S,B}$ can be expressed in terms of the optical one, $d_{A,B}$ since both depend on the *interior angle* β . Note that, $d_{A,S,B}$ is equal to $d_{A,S,B}=2l$, and the length l is related to β following (1). Thus, $T_{fs}(d_{A,S,B})$ in terms of $d_{A,B}$ will be:

$$T_{fs}(d_{A,B}) = \frac{2\sqrt{(R_E + h)^2 + R_E^2 - 2R_E(R_E + h)\cos\left(\frac{d_{A,B}}{2R_E}\right)}}{c}, \quad (5)$$

where in (5) has been used the relationship $\beta = d_{A,B}/(2R_E)$. Next, if (3) and (5) are plugged into (4), then the maximum distance, $d_{A,B}$, for using the optical fiber transport network instead of the satellite one is ruled by:

$$\frac{d_{A,B}^2 n_{of}^2}{4} + 2R_E(R_E + h)\cos\left(\frac{d_{A,B}}{2R_E}\right) - (R_E + h)^2 - R_E^2 < 0 \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2 represents the propagation time of the optical and satellite links in terms of the distance $d_{A,B}$ (*i.e.* the length of the arc between points A and B) when the altitude of the satellite is $h=600$ Km and $h=1200$ Km when the refraction index of the optical fiber is $n_{of}=1.46$. Based on this figure it is possible to observe that if $d_{A,B}$ is lower than 1178Km ($h=600$

Figure 3. Propagation time of the optical and satellite links when the satellite altitude is $h=600$ Km and $h=1200$ Km in terms of the elevation angle α .

Km) and 2467 Km ($h=1200$ Km), then the transport network with the lowest propagation time is the optical one. Otherwise, the satellite transport network has a lower propagation time. Note also that a higher satellite altitude reduces the benefit of its minor refraction index. Another interesting result is being able to express the propagation time of the optical and satellite links in terms of the elevation angle α . After obtaining $d_{A,B}$ from (6), the *interior angle* β is computed from the relationship $\beta = d_{A,B}/(2R_E)$ and finally, the elevation angle α is determined from (2). Similarly to Fig. 2, Fig. 3 shows the propagation times of the optical fiber and satellite networks in terms of the elevation angle of the satellite, α , when its altitude, h , is $h=600$ Km and $h=1200$ Km. Our results show that it is preferable to use satellite links when the elevation angle α is low. This situation happens when the distance $d_{A,B}$ is very large or when the satellite is at low altitudes. Finally, Fig. 4 shows the maximum altitude of the satellite for using the satellite transport network instead of the optical one in terms of the distance $d_{A,B}$. Note that the larger the distance $d_{A,B}$, the higher the maximum altitude where the satellite can be placed. Finally, after having presented how to select the optical and satellite networks, we will show in the following section how to determine the best regions to locate an optical ground station.

III. GROUND STATION LOCALIZATION ALGORITHM AND ITS PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION.

In the previous section we have answered the question on when to use the optical and satellite networks to connect points A and B when they are separated a distance $d_{A,B}$. When the network used is the satellite one, another question arises: *where to place the optical ground stations?*. Recall that it has been considered that the satellite should be optical for a grant comparison with the optical fiber in terms of bandwidth. Hence, this section has been divided in two parts. The explanation of the location-algorithm for the optical ground station and its efficient implementation to speed it up.

Figure 4. Maximum satellite altitude in terms of the distance $d_{A,B}$ for using satellite links instead of optical fiber.

A. Algorithm for Determining The Best Region for an Optical Ground Station.

Let I a matrix N_x and N_y which entry $I_{x,y}$ encompasses the color of a pixel in the horizontal and vertical axes. Each pixel (x,y) is represented by a tuple $t_{x,y}=[r_{x,y} \ g_{x,y} \ b_{x,y}]$ that contains the color of a pixel encoded in Reed Green Blue (RGB) format. The values of each component $r_{x,y}, g_{x,y}, b_{x,y}$ are ranged from 0 to 255. So, $I_{x,y}=t_{x,y} \ \forall x \in [1 \cdots N_x]$ and $y \in [1 \cdots N_y]$. Let, $t_{\text{ref,min}}=[r_{\text{ref,min}} \ g_{\text{ref,min}} \ b_{\text{ref,min}}]$ and $t_{\text{ref,max}}=[r_{\text{ref,max}} \ g_{\text{ref,max}} \ b_{\text{ref,max}}]$ be the minimum and maximum RGB color tuples of a cloud. Let R be the matrix which entries contain a 1 if the pixel (x,y) of the image I belongs to a cloud. Otherwise, it is a zero. Mathematically, it is formulated as:

$$R_{x,y} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t_{x,y} \in [t_{\text{ref,min}}, t_{\text{ref,max}}], \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Nevertheless, we do not have a single matrix but a set of N_q matrices since we have multiple images to process. Therefore, we will have to average (7) to obtain an estimation of finding clouds. In this regard, $\bar{R}_{x,y}$, denotes the averaged value of R for the (x,y) pixel and it is computed as

$$\bar{R}_{x,y} = \frac{1}{N_q} \sum_{k=1}^{N_q} R_{x,y,k}, \quad (8)$$

Note that in (8) all images have to represent the same geographical area. Otherwise, the results would be misleading. The outcome of this locating algorithm is a contour map that associates the regions of a geographical area with its probabilities on finding clouds in the band of the optical satellite. If there are N_s possible values for modeling such probabilities of finding clouds in a pixel (x,y) , then the quantized step of the probability states for finding clouds will be: $\Delta=1/N_s$. Then, the quantized $\bar{R}_{x,y}$, denoted as, $\tilde{R}_{x,y}$, is:

$$\tilde{R}_{x,y} = \lfloor \bar{R}_{x,y} / \Delta \rfloor \Delta \quad (9)$$

This process has to be repeated for the N_x and N_y horizontal and vertical pixels of the N_s images. Note that $\tilde{R}_{x,y}$ can only

be obtained once $\bar{R}_{x,y}$ has been computed. These constraints increase the latency of the program. For that reason the following section explains how to speed it up.

B. Efficient Implementation Issues.

The explained algorithm in previous section determines the probability of finding clouds in a geographical region. However, its direct implementation may take a lot of time. Initially, the program compared pixel by pixel its RGB value with a predetermined threshold for determining the existence of a cloud. Following this strategy we noted that it was necessary to distinguish between day and night images since they have different illumination properties which may lead to error their direct classification. In order to separate the images that are day from the night ones, we followed [13]. The satellite images are affected by the albedo of the surface, which makes some images more brighter and darker at the same time creating notable differences depending on the terrain. For further information about albedo issues, please see this reference [14]. In light of this findings, it was decided to just focus in the day light images. Thus, Fig.5 shows the structure of the Python program that was used. However, it was observed that a set of steps in Fig.5 were repeated for every image (*i.e.* brown boxes). Then, a second step was to parallelize these steps. In this regard, it was resorted to the OpenMP Python libraries. Thanks to that, the serial pixel by pixel analysis was replaced by a N_p pixel by pixel analysis, being N_p the number of cores that run in parallel. By doing so, it was obtained an outstanding saving in the execution time of the program. In order to evaluate the magnitude of this processing time reduction when N_p cores are used, two metrics were formulated: i) the expected time, T_{N_p} , and ii) the percentage of gain in the execution time, denoted as G_{N_p} . Both metrics are defined as:

$$T_{N_p} = \frac{T_s}{N_p} \quad ; \quad G_{N_p} = \frac{(T_s - T_{N_p}) \times 100}{T_s} \quad (10)$$

being T_s the execution time of the program that analyzes the images using a single core, *i.e.* $N_p=1$. Finally, after presenting the locating algorithm of the optical ground station and its efficient implementation we provide its results on the following section.

IV. RESULTS.

This section provides the following results: i) contour maps of the regions with a % of cloud appearance in the band of the optical satellite, and ii) processing time and gain in % when the program that analyzes the pixels uses N_p cores. As a paradigmatic case, it has been considered that the optical ground station is placed at the Iberian Peninsula. The downloaded EUMETSAT gray scale images belong to 3.9 nm wavelength band which may be used by an optical satellite. The photos were taken by METEOSAT Second Generation Satellite (MSG), a weather forecasting satellite. The data package from EUMETSAT is called "High Rate SEVIRI Level 1.5 Image Data - MSG - 0 degree". To study them, it was selected the 24th complete solar cycle, *i.e.* from 2011 to 2019.

Figure 5. Block diagram of the cloud system analyzer.

Thus, it is possible to study the cloud formation [15]. The interval between consecutive photos is 3 hours and the total amount of images to process is 35000. Finally, following the user's guide of EUMETSAT's package for these images [14], the minimum and maximum RGB values for selecting the pixels that belong to clouds were 0 and 27 respectively (note that 0 is black and 255 is white).

A. Cloud Analysis Program: Contour Maps.

Fig. 6 shows the contour maps after applying the parallel algorithm proposed in Section III for locating the optical ground station. In this figure it is possible to observe that the less cloudy areas are the ones located at the south of the Iberian Peninsula including Portugal. Specifically, in the regions from Spain of Extremadura, and Andalucía, and in the Portugal ones of Beja and Faro. In fact, Portugal has the lowest probability of having clouds with a 17%. On the contrary, the worst regions to collocate an optical ground station are sited on the mountains (*i.e.* the Pyrenees, the Central System, Sierra Nevada). It would be possible to have lower probabilities of finding clouds doing a more exhaustive cloud analysis and using diversity in the locations of the optical ground stations.

Figure 6. Contour map showing the probability of not finding clouds in the Iberian Peninsula. The least likely areas in dark blue and those with more, in red, intermediate percentage in white.

B. Processing time and gain of the Parallel Cloud Analysis Computation.

This section provides the processing time and gain of the program that analyzes the images when it uses N_p cores. The number of cores that have been used goes from one to twenty, *i.e.* $N_p \in [1 \dots 20]$. It has been tested in the CASTLE platform® of the Space and Resilient Communications System (SRCOM) unit [16]. This platform permits access via VPN and launch simulations over CASTLE platform® remotely. Toward this regard, Figs. 7 and 8, show the processing time and gain T_{N_p} and G_{N_p} formulated in (10). From there we observe that with a single core, the execution time of the program is $T_s = 1000s$. Nevertheless, if it is added other core, then the processing time is reduced to $T_2 = 500s$. Finally, if the program that analyzes the images uses $N_p = 20$ cores in parallel, then the total amount of processing time falls to $T_{20} = 84s$. It represents a saving of 91.67% of the execution time that a single core needs for processing all images (See Fig. 8). This represents a huge amount of saved time. Note in both figures that the obtained experimental results approach to the theoretical ones. Nonetheless, they are not exactly the same. This is due to the data exchange network of the parallel systems. If the number of cores increases, this network introduces a latency that may turn to the dominant delay. It is possible to observe this behaviour in Figs. 7-8 since the execution time of the program and its gain tend to a flat value with the increase of the number of cores.

V. CONCLUSIONS.

This work has been conducted under the umbrella of the research work of a baccalaureate student and so the conclusions are evaluated at two different levels: i) educational, and ii) technical. On the educational level, the benefits of bringing studies/research done by research centers closer to public education represents a great opportunity for students in the work that they conduct. On the other hand, it allows the updating of teachers' knowledge, as well as the integration of

Figure 7. Prac. and theo. execution time in terms of the cores to determine the best regions for an optical ground station in the Iberian peninsula.

Figure 8. Practical and theoretical gain in terms of the cores used to determine the best regions for locating an optical ground station in the Iberian peninsula.

this knowledge to the educational sphere. From the technical point of view the conclusions are also twofold: i) about when to use optical and satellite networks, and ii) where to locate an optical ground station. From the former, it has been shown that the larger value of the refraction index of the optical fiber impacts negatively in its viability when the distance to connect increases. In this situation is preferable to use a LEO/VLEO transport network. The waves through satellite networks travel larger distances than in the optical ones but they move faster, and therefore, arrive earlier to their final destination. Regarding the locating algorithm of the optical ground station, it has been obtained the regions at the Iberian Peninsula in which there is a certain probability of finding clouds at the optical wavelengths. For a single base station it has been obtained that the southwest part of the Iberian Peninsula provides the areas with the lowest probabilities of finding clouds. However, to have the large service availability probabilities required for 5G&beyond it will be necessary to install multiple optical ground stations. This part remains open as a future research line. Another issue

that has been considered is the efficient implementation of the optical ground station locating algorithm. Results indicate that it is mandatory to resort to parallel architectures to provide fast analysis when the proposed algorithm is used. Specially, if in the future it will be necessary to evaluate the position of multiples optical ground stations. At this point it becomes essential to remark that this work departs from the assumption that in the medium-long term the optical components of the satellites will improve as well as the efficiency of their architectures. Consequently, it will be possible in a close future to have optical LEO/VLEO satellites. By doing so, intercontinental communications at high speed could also be provided by mega-constellations of satellites in addition to the current optical submarine wires. Finally, for interplanetary connections (*e.g.* between Earth-Moon cities) this architecture would be of great utility.

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